

Taxonomic notes on Palaearctic longhorned beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae). Part. 3

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Key words: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, taxonomy, zoogeography, new synonyms, new status.

Abstract. 26 taxonomical remarks with new zoogeographical notes are proposed.

Introduction

These notes are a continuation of a series of comments previously published in two my articles (Lazarev, 2024a, 2024b). Now I've proposed several new synonyms and several new geographical records, several records are corrected, certain synonyms are restored as valid names, several published novations are accepted, others are rejected; several new names are declared as unavailable.

Results

1. *Mesoprionus* Jakovlev, 1887: 323 = *Trispinicollis* Özdikmen, 2025c: 3001 type species *Prionus besikanus* Fairmaire, 1855, **syn. nov.**

2. *Euracmaeops* (*Pilosoacmaeops* Özdikmen, 2025b: 1985, 1986 type species *Pachyta angusticollis* Fabricius, 1781) is accepted with two species: *E. (P.) angusticollis* (Fabricius, 1781) and *E. (P.) smaragdulus* (Fabricius, 1793).

3. Kulenko (2015: 1094) first reported a specimen of *Alosterna ingrlica* (Baekmann 1902) from Samara Region (Gremyachy,

M.A. Lazarev

53°26'44"N 48°09'28"E). Recently, another specimen was found in the collection of V. Ustinov (Moscow, Russia) with label: "RUS. Samara reg., ZHIGULI / Nat. Res, kordon Churakayka, / 53.325°N 48.829°E / 22-30.V.2023 K.P. Tomkovich".

4. According to Sama (2003), males of *Pachytodes erraticus* (Dalman, 1817) are often with red (or reddish) elytral apex. Such form was described as *Pachyta erythrura* Küster, 1848 and is sometimes retained as species. It is "the usual form of males in southern part of the distribution area". I know such males from Bulgaria, Moldavia Georgia & Armenia, where it occurs together with typical males. So, *Pachytodes erraticus erythrurus* (Küster, 1848), name rest. is a valid name of southern subspecies (type locality: Turkey), distributed in Turkey, Transcaucasia and southern Europe.

5. *Vadonia* (*Sinemaculipenna* Özdikmen, 2025i: 2989 type species *Vadonia instigmata* Pic, 1889) is characterized by serrated antennae and includes four species only: *V. (S.) instigmata* Pic, 1890, *V. (S.) bicolor* (L. Redtenbacher, 1850), *V. (S.) bitlisiensis* Chevrolat, 1882, *V. (S.) ispirensis* Holzschuh, 1993.

6. The transfer of *Aeolesthes sarta* (Solsky, 1871) to *Trirachys* by Vitali, Gouverneur & Chemin (2017) looks artificial. *A. sarta* is very similar to the type species of the genus *Aeolesthes* Gahan, 1890 - *Aeolesthes aurifaber* (White, 1853) by several characters: male antennae in *A. sarta* without spines (only females have spines), while in *Trirachys orientalis* Hope, 1842 (type species of *Trirachys* Hope, 1842) male antennae with long internal spines; prothorax in *A. sarta* without lateral spines, but in *T. orientalis* - with well-developed spines; outer angles of elytral apices in *A. sarta* without spines, but in *T. orientalis* - with spines.

7. *Rosalia* Audinet-Serville, 1834 = *Rosaliaoides* Özdikmen, 2025f: 3308 type species *Rosalia batesi* Harold, 1877, **syn. nov.**

8. *Purpuricenus* (*Basiatropansexus* Özdikmen, 2025g: 2789 type species *Cerambyx kaehleri* Linnaeus, 1758) was proposed for 22 very different species from Europe, Asia, Africa and North

M.A. Lazarev

America. The type species designation was just a misprint. Correct designation was shown on page 2782 in the subscription to Fig. 4: “*Purpuricenus barbarous* Lucas, 1842 as type species and an example of the species group A of the new subgenus *Purpuricenus* (*Basiatropansexus*) subgen. nov.”.

The separation of two subgenera *P.* (s. str.) and *P.* (*Basiatropansexus* Özdikmen, 2025g) was based on the color of elytral humeral area only, and so was quite artificial: *Purpuricenus* Dejean, 1821 = *Basiatropansexus* Özdikmen, 2025g, **syn. nov.**

9. *Purpuricenus kykladicus* Vartanis, 2023d, *Brachyta alpina* Vartanis, 2025, *Cerambyx cerdo cyprius* Vartanis, 2023a and *Anaglyptus rubrucollis* Vartanis, 2025 (published as *rubrucollum*) are unavailable names - no information on type deposition was published. Other descriptions must be proposed.

The name *Chlorophorus varius macedonicus* Vartanis, 2023c was described without information on holotype deposition and so, unavailable. A part of paratypes only were attributed to the collection of J. Vartanis. Another description must be proposed.

The data on types depositions of *Stictoleptura olympicola* Vartanis, 2023, *Ropalopus criticus* Vartanis, 2024 and *Ropalopus insubricus olympicus* Vartanis, 2024c were uncertain.

10. *Anubis* J. Thomson, 1864: 177 = *Divinus* Özdikmen, 2025e: 2721 type species *Anubis rostratus* Bates, 1879, **syn. nov.**

11. The name *Deilosoma* traditionally addressed to Fairmaire (1864: 804) with type species *Callidium fugax* Olivier, 1790) is unavailable; see records by Gemminger, 1872: 2899; Scudder, 1882, 1: 102, 2: 93 - “*Deilosoma* Fairmaire. Gen. Col., iv, p. 804. Col.”; Aurivillius (1912: 294).

The name was declared as unavailable by Löbl & Smetana (2010: 59): “*Deilosoma* Fairmaire, 1864: 804 (type species *Callidium fugax* Olivier, 1790) is currently listed as an invalid synonym of *Deilus* Audinet-Serville, 1834, and as published in the volume 4 of Jacquelin du Val's *Genera des Coleopteres d'Europe ...* None of the

M.A. Lazarev

volumes of these Genera has so high pagination, and the name does not appear in any of the volumes. *Deiosoma* Fairmaire remains untraceable and is therefore considered as a nomen nudum.” Probably the first, who published *Deilosoma* was Gemminger (1872: 2899).

12. *Stenopterus flavicornis* Küster, 1846 was recorded by Zamoroka & Panin (2011: 160) for Africa with reference to “Sama et al, 2005”, as well as for Caucasus with reference to Althoff & Danilevsky (1997). The corresponding publications don’t containe such records, and the species is absent in Africa, neither in Caucasus.

13. *Stenopterus* Illiger, 1804 = *Stenopterus (Bicallosocollus)* Özdikmen, 2025h: 2766 type species *Stenopterus flavicornis* Küster, 1846), **syn. nov.**

14. *Anaglyptus* Mulsant, 1839: 91 = *Aglaophisoides* Özdikmen, 2025d: 2699 type species *Anaglyptus graphellus* Holzschuh, 2011 = *Maculiglyptus* Özdikmen, 2025d: 2700 type species *Oligoenoplus annulicornis* Pic, 1933 = *Variiglyptus* Özdikmen, 2025d: 2701 type species *Anaglyptus niponensis* Bates, 1884, **syn. nn.**

15. According to Fu et al. (2024), genus *Chlorophorus* is monophyletic.

16. *Dorcadion obtusum kostali* Özdikmen & Skoupý, 2025: 3172 is unavailable name - the collection of the holotype preservation was not published. Another description must be proposed.

17. According to Danilevsky & Tavakilian (2022), *Cerambyx taeniatus* Gmelin, 1790 = *Leiopus linnei* Wallin, Nylander & Kwamme, 2009. According to Kwamme, Wallin & Sörensson (2024), *Cerambyx taeniatus* Gmelin, 1790 = *Cerambyx punctulatus* Paykull, 1800. The only possibility to fix the contradiction is the study of the sketch in the original description of *C. taeniatus* Gmelin, 1790. The main and a single reason to connect the original picture with *Leiopus punctulatus* (Paykull, 1800) is the big antennal length in the picture, which is really too much for *L. linnei*, but similar to *L. punctulatus*. But in fact, the published picture is rather far from the reality: big

M.A. Lazarev

width of the prothorax is impossible in the genus, the shape of tarsi joints is fantastic. From the other side, narrowed in the middle black elytral band is a character of *L. linnei*, as well as pale apices of antennal joints, and pale elytral bases. Finally, I prefer to regard: *Cerambyx taeniatus* Gmelin, 1790 = *Leiopus linnei* Wallin, Nylander & Kvamme, 2009.

It is impossible to declare the oldest name as forgotten, because it was recently used as available (Bartenev, 2004: 38; 2009: 329; Breuning, 1963: 555; 1978: 64; Villiers, 1978: 492; Vives & Alonso-Zarazaga, 2000: 642; Özdikmen, 2007: 318; Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 209; Dunska & Barševskis, 2018: 186 - all as *L. nebulosus* Linnaeus, 1758) or valid (Danilevsky & Tavakilian, 2022: 131; Danilevsky, 2023: 378; 2024: 126). Anyway, the traditional point of view: *L. nebulosus* = *L. taeniatus* was generally accepted.

18. *Anaesthetis flavipilis* Baeckmann, 1903 was recorded for Khakassia (Abakan environs) by Kuleshov (2025) on the bases of a single male. Most probably it was a new species.

19. Several new names by Özdikmen, 2025 are accepted:

Pachyteria (*Tripartocorna* Özdikmen, 2025j: 2745 type species *Pachyteria ruficollis* Waterhouse, 1878) with two species: *P. (T.) equestris* (Newman, 1841) and *P. (T.) semiplicata* Pic, 1927

Stenhomalus (*Bicoloripennus* Özdikmen, 2025k: 2622 type species *Stenhomalus coomani* Gressitt, 1951) with fore species: *S. (B.) coomani* Gressitt, 1951; *S. (B.) dayaoshanus* Niisato & Chou, 2018; *S. (B.) mirificus* Niisato & Chou, 2018; *S. (B.) ruficollis* Gressitt, 1935.

Stenhomalus (*Unicoloripennus* Özdikmen, 2025k: 2625 type species *Obrium longicorne* Bates, 1873) with ten species: *S. (U.) incongruus incongruus* Gressitt, 1939; *S. (U.) incongruus muneaka* Hayashi, 1981; *S. (U.) incongruus parallelus* Niisato, 1988; *S. (U.) japonicus* (Pic, 1904); *liui* Niisato, 2015; *S. (U.) longicornis* (Bates, 1873); *S. (U.) nagaoui* Hayashi, 1960; *(U.) pallidus* Gressitt,

M.A. Lazarev

1935; *S. (U.) pinicola* Holzschuh, 2015; *S. (U.) takaosanus* K. Ohbayashi, 1958; *S. (U.) tetricus* Holzschuh, 2007; *S. (U.) unicolor* Niisato & Hua, 1998.

Anamera (Longipenna Özdikmen, 2025l: 2874 type species *Anamera gigantea* Breuning, 1935) with one species: *A. (L.) gigantea gigantea* Breuning, 1935; *A. (L.) gigantea iliyashenkoi* Jiroux, Garreau & Gurko, 2012.

Aristobia (Sinicapillosa Özdikmen, 2025l: 2878 type species *Lamia reticulator* Fabricius, 1781) with eight species: *A. (S.) angustifrons* Gahan, 1888; *A. (S.) approximator* (J. Thomson, 1865); *A. (S.) freneyi* Schmitt, 1992; *A. (S.) hispida* (Saunders, 1853); *A. (S.) horridula* (Hope, 1831); *A. (S.) reticulator* (Fabricius, 1781); *A. (S.) vietnamensis* Breuning, 1972; *A. (S.) voettii* J. Thomson, 1878.

Thermistis (Atroapicipennis Özdikmen, 2025o: 3106 type species *Thermistis taiwanensis* Nara & Yu, 1992) with four species: *T. (A.) cheni* Lin & Chou, 2012; *T. (A.) rubromaculata* Pu, 1984; *T. (A.) sulphureonotata* Pu, 1984; *T. (A.) taiwanensis* Nara & S.-K. Yu, 1992.

Phytoecia (Neomusarioides Özdikmen, 2025m: 1800, type species *Saperda modesta* Waltl, 1838 = *Neomusaria waltli* Sama, 1991) with four species: *Ph. (N.) furkani* H.Özdikmen & G.Özdikmen, 2016; *Ph. (N.) pauliraputii* (Sama, 1993); *Ph. (N.) shokhini* Kasatkin, 2010; *Ph. (N.) waltli* Sama, 1991.

Phytoecia (Metallicophytoecia Özdikmen, 2025n: 1819 type species *Leptura caerulea* Scopoli, 1772) with four species: *Ph. (Me.) caerulea baccueti* (Brullé, 1832); *Ph. (Me.) caerulea bethseba* Reiche & Saulcy, 1858; *Ph. (Me.) caerulea caerulea* (Scopoli, 1772); *Ph. (Me.) caerulea viridipes* Rapuzzi & Sama, 2018: 24; *Ph. (Me.) coeruleipennis* Breuning, 1947; *Ph. (Me.) coeruleomicans* Breuning, 1947; *Ph. (Me.) malachitica* P. H. Lucas, 1847.

20. According to Zamoroka & Zinenko (2024), “In Europe, *Tetrops*

M.A. Lazarev

is represented by four species: *Tetrops praeustus* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Tetrops gilvipes* (Faldermann, 1837), *Tetrops starkii* Chevrolat, 1859, and *Tetrops peterkai* Skořepa, 2020.” *T. praetermitus* Sláma, 2020 (described from Slovakia) was omitted.

21. One male of *Oberea (Amaurostoma) histrionis* Pic, 1917 (Fig. 1) (S Russia, Rostov-on-Don, Mityakinskaya, 25.5.1997, P. Ivliev) is preserved in the collection of M.A. Lazarev (Moscow).

24. Four species were erroneously transferred to *Phytoecia (Neomusaria)* from *Phytoecia* (s. str.) by Özdikmen (2025a): *Phytoecia napolovi* Danilevsky, 2012; *Phytoecia annulipes* Mulsant & Rey, 1863; *Phytoecia marki* Danilevsky, 2008; *Phytoecia martinae* Danilevsky & Hodek, 2021.

25. One female of *Phytoecia* (s.str.) *cylindrica* from Mongolia (aimak Arkhangay, Tevshruleg, 13.7.1973, L. Medvedev) is preserved in Murzin’s collection (Moscow).

26. *Phytoecia* (s. str.) *geniculata* Mulsant, 1862 (described from “la Turquie”) consists (up to now) of two rather different subspecies. Nominative subspecies is characterized by much more red femora: about apical third, half or more than a half of each femora is red (in my collection: Athens environs, Mersin, Lorestan). It is distributed in Greece, Bulgaria, Romania, Anatolia, Cyprus and Iran (absent in Caucasus); elytral pubescence very fine, nearly indistinct, so elytra look black; pronotum nearly glabrous. *Ph.* (s. str.) *g. nazarena* Reiche, 1877b, **stat. n.** (described from Nazareth) (Figs 2-3) has about totally black middle and hind femora with red apices only; anterior femora with red apical third (anterior tibiae totally red); pale elytral pubescence denser and elytra look grey; pronotum with well developed pale setae central stripe (in my collection: big series from near Haifa, Israel). It is distributed in Israel, Lebanon, Syria and Jordan.

So, *Ph. geniculata* looks as:

geniculata geniculata Mulsant, 1862: 420 (“la Turquie”) E: BU CY GR IN RO TR

donatellae Rapuzzi & Sama, 2010: 187 (“Grecia, Joannina: Passo est Konitsa”)

fuscicornis Mulsant & Rey, 1863: 168 [HN] (“La Grèce, les environs de

M.A. Lazarev

Constantinople")

orientalis Kraatz, 1871: 272 [RN] ("Griechenland und der Türkei")

geniculata nazarena Reiche, 1877: cxxxvi ("Nazareth in Palaestina")

A: ?IQ IS JO LE SY ?TR

ingeniculata T. Pic, 1900: 67 ("Syria: St. Jean d'Acre")

palaestina Pic, 1930: 3 ("Jérusalem")

Fig. 1. *Oberea (Amaurostoma) histrionis* Pic, 1917: S Russia, Rostov-on-Don, Mityakinskaya, 25.5.1997, P. Ivliev.

Figs 2-3. *Phytoecia* (s. str.) *geniculata nazarena* Reiche, 1877: 2. male, Israel, Haifa, 11.4.1993, A. Danchenko; 3. Female, Israel, Kibz., Dahila, 30.3.1975, O. Mehl

M.A. Lazarev

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M.A. Lazarev

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M.A. Lazarev

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M.A. Lazarev

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Received: 28.06.2025

Accepted: 04.07.2025